

Role of Social Support in Work Motivation and Quality of Work Life among Working Women in Haryana

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While people go to work and get ready for a better future; many parts of their lives are put on hold. Work Motivation and Quality of work life of a person, especially in the case of working women are determining factors of their success in work life and workplace. This empirical study aims to examine how social support affects the level of work motivation and work-life quality of working women in Haryana. Our study has a sample of 200 (clerk=50, corporate=50, nurse=50, teachers=50) from different institutions of Haryana and Delhi regions. Subjects were assessed using psychometric tools including the Work Motivation Questionnaire (WMQ-A) by Agarwal the 1971, Quality of Work Life Scale (QWLS) by Dhar et al. (1971) and the Multidimensional Scale for Perceived Social Support by Gregory Zimet et al. (1988) and correlational analysis was used to test the hypotheses. Results of research reveal that social support is positively correlated with work motivation and work-life quality in working women. There is also found a positive correlation between work motivation and quality of work life.

Keywords: social support, work motivation, working women, quality of work life, workplace

In the past, women were held in the highest regard and were revered as goddesses and divine favours. The Vedic tradition accords women with the highest respect possible since it considers them to be the manifestation of numerous significant characteristics and abilities. According to Manusmriti 3.5559, "where women are worshipped, there the gods dwell," which promotes female protection and empowerment. India's history has seen a tremendous contribution from women. Some notable Indian women's contributions include: Ahilyabai Holker, Sarojini Naidu, Indira Gandhi, and Kaplan Chawla are all important figures in India's history. Ahilyabai Holker advocated industry and spread the dharma, Sarojini Naidu was a political activist and poet, and Indira Gandhi was the first female prime minister. She was the country's first female prime minister to hold office for three terms in a row. Kalpana Chawla was the first female astronaut of Indian ancestry and inspired young people to pursue careers in spaceflight. Lakshmi et al. (2018) discovered that married working women, regardless of the industry, age group, number of children,

and spouse's job, find it challenging to manage their studies and personal lives. Professionals working in the IT sector face more challenges than female employees working in the academic and healthcare sectors. Couples in the business and marketing industries suffer the most, despite the notion that work-life balance is the key to happiness and a fulfilling life. According to this study, employees' work-life balance was significantly influenced by their vocations, ages, and care obligations as well as their weekly work hours and work-related stress. Compared to men, women report increased stress, headaches, muscular aches, weight gain, and depression.

Holland and Cortina (2016) have found that workplace sexual harassment is an unlawful and immoral behaviour that hurts not just the women, who are harassed, but also their coworkers, workgroups, and entire organizations. Until the situation changes, sexual and gender-based harassment will pose a serious threat to the health and well-being of working women. According to Schaefer et. al. (2002), "social support can be defined in terms of information or social environmental conditions that in turn enable an individual to feel loved and cared for, affirmed or as belonging to a group of persons with common goals and beliefs". In the last three decades, social support has come to be the center of study interest. Dean and Lin (1977) consider social support as a function of primary groups that meet instrumental and also expressive needs. It is one of the main components that a working woman needs to handle all the job requirements and also other personal roles she has in his life. Social support is always considered a multi-dimensional construct. Social support affects both the personal and work life of an individual. As we live in a country like India social support is very much important in terms of social acceptance of what we do. Additionally, it has been observed that working women leave their jobs when there is a lack of social acceptance and support because some cultures do not recognise the fact that women can hold paid employment. They believe they have enough resources to live comfortably, so they don't see the need for women to work.

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Social Support and Work Motivation

Budd and Bhawe (2010) defined “work as a purposeful human activity involving physical or mental exertion that is not undertaken solely for pleasure and that has economic value”. Salary and other perks, the desire for prestige and recognition, a sense of accomplishment, relationships with coworkers, and the conviction that one's work matters all serve as motivating factors (Osabiya, 2015). According to research by Sarwar and Khalid (2015), nurses who worked the day shift rated their perceived social support and work motivation as being higher than those who worked the night shift. Additionally, night shift nurses noted more physical and psychological difficulties as well as more complaints and fewer nurses opted to work the night shift. Perceived organizational support predicts job motivation, and this element, as well as organizational commitment, are related. The social work environment is essential in the nursing industry, and there is a connection between long workdays, fatigue, and errors.

Wicaksono (2021) carried out a study to investigate the Relationship between Work-family Conflict, Work Motivation, and Social Support to East Java Province Government Organization's Performance of ASN Women. The interplay of work-family conflict, job motivation, and social support has a significant positive effect on how well female public workers perform in East Java Provincial Government Organisations. The more social support there is, the more motivated people are at work.

Social Support and Quality of Work Life

Quality of life, according to the Collins Dictionary (2017), is "the general well-being of a person or society", defined in terms of health and happiness rather than wealth. “This concept gives more importance to who they are than what they have. It covers the emotional side rather than the material one. Wealth is not as significant as one's degree of comfort or contentment or that of society. But there is no denying that the fulfilment of our basic physical needs is crucial for our well-being. In other words, well-being is the result of a continuous process that begins with the physical and moves on to the psychological, social, and spiritual domains.

Fiorilli et al. (2016) looked at the connections between teachers' social support, burnout levels, and emotional competence. They found that while teachers' ability to control their emotions has no relationship to any of the dimensions of burnout, the intensity of their emotions after an incident that threatens their sense of efficacy is positively associated with emotional exhaustion and negatively associated with personal accomplishment. Emotional labour has a tight connection to burnout syndrome, which can make both internal and external social support less satisfying. Asnani et al. (2004) concluded that social support is essential for lowering stress levels, enhancing health, and reducing the negative effects of stress on health. Working women can benefit from supportive social environments, teaching them to seek out social support, providing instrumental support, and providing emotional support from the organisation.

Objective of the Study

- To study the relationship between social support and work motivation among working women in Haryana
- To study the relationship between social support and quality of

work life among working women in Haryana

Hypotheses of the Study

- There shall be a positive relationship between social support and work motivation among working women in Haryana
- There is shall be a positive relationship between social support and quality of work life among working women in Haryana

Method

Participants

A sample of 200 working women was taken. The sample was collected from different districts of Haryana. The sample was divided into four categories Teachers, 50 Clerks, 50 Corporate Managers and 50 Nurses. The data consists of women aged 20-50 working in different sectors of Haryana.

Measures

Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) (Zimet et al., 1988): There are 12 statements on this scale. There are seven options for each statement that is - very strongly disagree, strongly disagree, mildly disagree, neutral, mildly agree, strongly agree, and very strongly agree. Also, the three dimensions of this scale are the significant other subscale, family subscale, and friends subscale. This dimension shows the individual getting support from family, friends and significant other in his/ her life. The internal reliability of the total scale was .88 and the test-retest reliability value was .85 with high validity value.

Work Motivation Questionnaire (WMQ-A) (Agarwal, 1971): There are 26 statements, having five alternative options to answer and six factors or dimensions namely dependence, organizational orientation, workgroup relation, psychological work incentives, material incentives, and job situation. These dimensions show the kind of motivation an individual is getting in his/ her organisation or work setting. The reliability value obtained by the Spearman-Brown formula was .99 and factor validity of the scale varied from .24 - .67.

Quality of Work Life Scale (QWLS) (Dhar et al., 1971): Here, the statements are 45 which have five alternative options that are - strongly disagree, disagree, not sure, agree, and strongly agree. And there are four dimensions which are - protective, work-life balance, human relations, and learning organisation. These dimensions show the quality of work life he/she is living. This is a highly reliable and valid scale, the reliability of scales measured by the test-retest method.

Results and Discussion

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Protectively	71.94	10.852	201
Work-life balance	54.75	8.263	201
Human Relations	15.58	6.411	201
Learn Organization	19.37	2.459	201
Quality of work life	161.64	24.114	201
Work motivation	89.64	15.061	201
Social support	3.45	.681	201

This table presents descriptive statistics for seven variables:

"Protectively," "Work life balance," "Human Relations," "Learn Organization," "Quality of work life," "Work motivation," and "Social support." Here's what each statistic means:

The mean represents the average value of the variable. It is determined by adding up all the values and dividing the result by the total number of observations. Std. Deviation The variability or dispersion of the data points around the mean is measured by the standard deviation. It provides information about how spreads out the values are from the average. N represents the sample size, which indicates the number of observations or data points used to calculate the mean and standard deviation.

Here, Protectivity, which measures the level of protection employees feel at work, has a standard deviation of 10.852 and an average (mean) score of 71.94. These values show that, on average, employees reported a moderate level of Protectivity, with a moderate amount of variability in their responses. The data is based on 201 observations. The variable work-life balance, which reflects the extent to which work and personal life are balanced, has a standard deviation of 8.263 and a mean score of 54.75. This suggests that, on average, employees perceived their work-life balance to be slightly above the midpoint of the scale. The standard deviation indicates a moderate amount of variability in employees' perceptions of work-life balance. A human relationship, which assesses the quality of interpersonal relationships at work, has a standard deviation of 6.411 and an average score of 15.58. These values indicate that, on average, employees reported a moderate level of human relations, with some

variability in their responses. The variable learning organization, which measures the extent to which the organization promotes continuous learning, has a standard deviation of 2.459 and a mean score of 19.37, this suggests that, on average, employees perceived their organization to have a relatively high level of emphasis on learning.

The standard deviation indicates a relatively low amount of variability in employee opinions on the learning corporation. Life quality at work, which evaluates the overall satisfaction with various aspects of work, has an average score of 161.64 and a standard deviation of 24.114. These values indicate that, on average, employees reported a relatively high level of satisfaction with their work life. The standard deviation suggests a moderate amount of variability in employees' perceptions of the life quality at work. Work motivation, which measures the level of motivation employees experience at work, has a standard deviation of 15.061 and an average score of 89.64. This indicates that, on average, employees reported a relatively high level of work motivation. The standard deviation suggests a moderate amount of variability in employees' levels of work motivation.

Lastly, social support, which assesses the perceived level of support from colleagues and supervisors, is having a standard deviation of 0.681 and a mean score of 3.45. These values specify that, on average, employees reported a moderate level of social support. The standard deviation suggests a relatively low amount of variability in employees' perceptions of social support.

Table 2

Correlation Analyses

Sr. no	Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Social support	1	.249**	.371**	.439**	.349**	.071	.346**
2	Work motivation		1	.473**	.447**	.492**	.191**	.383**
3	Quality of work life			1	.948**	.942**	.634**	.803**
4	Protectivity				1	.898**	.408**	.801**
5	Work-life balance					1	.447**	.750**
6	Human Relations						1	.313**
7	Learn Organization							1

Note. ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

This table shows the correlations between seven different factors. Social support, work motivation, life quality at work, Protectivity, work-life balance, human relations, and learning organization, These correlation coefficients represent the direction and strength of the relationships between each pair of variables. Social support shows significant positive correlations with work motivation (0.249**), quality of work life (0.371**), Protectivity (0.439**), work-life balance (0.349**), and learning organization (0.346**). However, the correlation with human relations is relatively weak (0.071). Moving on to work motivation, it demonstrates significant positive correlations with quality of work life (0.473**), Protectivity (0.447**), work-life balance (0.492**), and learning organization (0.383**). The correlation with human relations is also positive but relatively weaker (0.191**). Quality of work life, exhibits strong positive correlations with Protectivity (0.948**), work-life balance (0.942**), and learning organization (0.803**).

The correlation with human relations is also significant but

moderately lower (0.634**). Protectivity displays a substantial positive correlation with work-life balance (0.898**), a moderate positive correlation with human relations (0.408**), and a strong positive correlation with learning organization (0.801**). Work-life balance demonstrates a significant positive correlation with human relations (0.447**) and a strong positive correlation with learning organization (0.750**). Human relations has a moderate positive correlation with learning organization (0.313**). Lastly, learning organization is not correlated with any other variables in the table. In summary, the table reveals various significant positive correlations among the variables.

Factors like social support, work motivation, life quality at work, Protectivity, balance in work-life and human relations show positive associations with each other. The strongest relationships are observed between the quality of life at work and Protectivity, work-life balance, and learning organization. Work motivation also has strong positive associations with quality of life at work,

productivity, work-life balance, and learning organization. On the other hand, variables like social support and human relations exhibit weaker correlations with other variables. These findings provide valuable insights into the interrelationships between different factors and can be useful for understanding the dynamics and impact of these variables in the given context.

The research aimed to inspect how social support influences the motivation levels and overall life quality of women in the workplace in Haryana. The study used three scales to collect data: the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) to measure social support, the Work Motivation Questionnaire (WMQ-A) to assess work motivation, and the Life quality at work Scale (QWLS) to evaluate the quality of work life. Descriptive statistics were presented to provide an overview of the responses. The mean values indicated the average levels of each variable, while the standard deviation indicated the variability or spread of responses.

A relationship analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between variables. The correlation coefficients indicated the strength and direction of the relationships. Positive correlations were found between social support and work motivation, social support and life quality at work, as well as between work motivation and work-life quality. In summary, the study found that social support positively influenced work motivation and quality of work life among working women in Haryana. The outcomes highlight the significance of providing social support to enhance work motivation and improve the overall work experience for women in the workplace.

Limitations of the Study

Sample Size and Generalizability: The findings may not be as generalizable as they may have been because the study used a limited sample size. The outcomes might not be an accurate reflection of all working women in Haryana or may not apply to other regions or cultures.

Self-report Measures: The data collection relied on self-report measures, which can introduce response biases. The data's validity and reliability could have been impacted by participants' use of false or socially acceptable responses while answering questions about their experiences.

Social Desirability Bias: Participants might have responded in a way that aligns with societal expectations or norms. This bias could influence their ratings of social support, work motivation, and work-life quality, potentially affecting the accuracy of the results.

Cultural Specificity: The study was conducted in Haryana, India, which has its unique cultural and social context. The findings may be influenced by specific cultural factors that do not apply to other regions or countries. It is important to consider the cultural context when interpreting and applying the results to different settings.

Lack of Control Variables: The research may not have considered certain variables that could impact the relationship between work motivation, social support, and work-life quality. Factors such as job type, organizational culture, or personal characteristics were not accounted for, which could have influenced the observed associations.

Limited Scope: The study focused specifically on working women in Haryana, which may limit the generalizability to other genders or populations. The findings may not be directly applicable to men or women in different employment settings or sectors.

Acknowledging these limitations helps to contextualize the research and encourages further investigation to strengthen the understanding of social support, work motivation, and quality of work life among diverse populations.

Conclusion and Future Implication of the Study

The study's implications include policy and workplace interventions to improve the work environment for women, focusing on fostering a supportive work culture, elastic work arrangements, and work-life balance. It also emphasizes the importance of gender equality, promoting equal opportunities, fair treatment, and access to resources for women in the workforce. Organizations can use the findings to design and implement employee assistance programs that target women's needs, offering support services, counselling, mentoring, and resources. Training and skill development programs are crucial for working women, and longitudinal research is needed to examine the dynamic nature of social support, work motivation, and quality of work life. Cross-cultural studies can also provide valuable insights into the influence of cultural, social, and organizational factors on working women's experiences. Intersectional perspectives are essential, as examining how social support, work motivation, and quality of work life intersect with various dimensions of identity can highlight the unique experiences and challenges faced by diverse groups of working women. By incorporating these implications, researchers, policymakers, and organizations can contribute to creating more supportive and empowering work environments for women, fostering gender equality, and enhancing overall well-being and job satisfaction among working women.

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